

Deliverable 3.2: DIH Community, vision and mission

Grant Agreement Number	825640
Project Acronym	DIHNET.EU
Deliverable Date	1 November2019
Authors	Begoña Sanchez (TECNALIA)
Number of Pages	16
Number of Annexes	0
Version	1.0
Reviewed by	Ruud Baartmans, Kristina Karanikolova, Mayte Carracedo, Lucie Milcent
Approved by	The consortium
Dissemination level	Public

The overall aim of DIHNET.EU is to create a sustainable European network of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), by developing a set of tools and boosting the collaboration of the different DIH networks, DIHs and other key DIH stakeholders in Europe. The project will act as a coordinator to enhance the collaboration, aligning and synchronizing their activities. This is considered crucial for a better support of SMEs and MidCap companies in offering and using digitisation services.

The project is carried out by TNO, TECNALIA, Fundingbox, euRobotics, BluMorpho and FEDIL, have strong experience in DIHs and well connected to the EU DIH community.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 825640.
www.dihnet.eu

Executive Summary

DIHNET.EU aims to create a sustainable European network of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), by developing a set of tools and by boosting the collaboration between the different DIH networks, DIHs and other key DIH stakeholders in Europe.

D 3.2: DIH Community, vision and mission is framed under **WP3: Upgrade of the Catalogue; Task 3.2: From the Catalogue to the DIH Community**. The objective of this Deliverable is to set a vision and a mission for the Community of DIHNET.EU project. This taking as a basis among others the JRC Catalogue and the DIH assessment performed; the Community building and grow with new DIHs, most of them part of the Catalogue and DIH networks; understanding the DIH needs to keep a dynamic and connective Community, where DIHs can interact and grow. A survey has been launched online at the Community to know demands and interest from DIHs.

This Deliverable is structured in three main Chapters:

- Chapter 1: sets the context of the Deliverable.
- Chapter 2: presents the vision and mission.
- Chapter 3: explains the activities in place to reach the Community mission and vision.
- Chapter 4: provides some concluding remarks.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary.....	2
1 Introduction	4
1.1 About DIHNET.EU.....	4
1.2 Context of Deliverable 3.2	4
1.3 Objectives of Deliverable 3.2	5
2 DIH Community, vision and mission for the DIHNET Community	8
3 Activities supporting to reach the DIHNET Community mission and vision	10
3.1. The DIHs assessment under the JRC platform	10
3.2. Identification and Classification of the Community Groups	11
3.3. DIHNET.EU Working groups as facilitators	12
3.4. Understanding the Community needs and demands	13
3.5. Community Planning and alignment.....	14
3.6. Coherence with regional, national and EU policies	15
4 Conclusions	16

1 Introduction

1.1 About DIHNET.EU

The **overall aim of DIHNET.EU** is to create a sustainable European network of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), by developing a set of tools and by boosting the collaboration of the different DIH networks, DIHs and other key DIH stakeholders in Europe. The project will act as a coordinator to enhance the collaboration, aligning and synchronizing their activities. This is considered crucial for a better support of SMEs and MidCap companies in offering and using digitisation services.

This **Deliverable** is key for the project, as it focuses on setting the mission and vision of the Community of DIHs, taking as a basis all the work previously done in the project during the first 12 months. This Deliverable supports and enhances the collaboration among DIHs on specific topics and connects to the Catalogue. The idea is to progress from the Catalogue to the Community, as an alive instrument that supports the Catalogue. It is a key Deliverable to reach the scope of DIHNET.EU project.

The project is coordinated by TNO and implemented together with Tecnalia, Fundingbox, euRobotics (EB), BLUMORPHO (BM) and FEDIL, partners with strong experience on the field.

1.2 Context of Deliverable 3.2

Deliverable 3.2: DIH Community, vision and mission is framed under WP3: Upgrade of the Catalogue; Task 3.2: From the Catalogue to the DIH Community, coordinated by TECNALIA and with contributions from FBA, TNO, EB, FEDIL. The task has been implemented from M1 to M12 and the Deliverable is submitted on time in M12 (1 November 2019).

The **main objective of this WP3** is to **upgrade the Catalogue of DIHs** by identifying, supporting and reinforcing the collaboration activities and capacities of the DIHs. Therefore, to support the creation of a sustainable network of specialised DIHs. Based on the Catalogue, the individual DIHs will better network and create a dynamic European DIH Community. The specific objectives are:

- To provide a **common framework** for the upgrade and update of the information provided by the Catalogue, by defining a structured approach to collect and update information from DIHs.
- To initiate the actual **upgrade of the Catalogue** in cooperation with other DIH agents and individual DIHs.
- To create an **overview of the European DIH landscape** that can be fed into the further collaboration activities.
- To suggest **Working Groups** to make the EU DIH Community active (feeding from WP1).
- To provide a common approach for DIH Maturity Assessment leading to improved learning and exchange of experiences.

WP3 is implemented in close cooperation with JRC/IPTS as JRC is nowadays working on the Catalogue, DG Connect as well as with other relevant and related DIH networks and projects. The connection to the DIHs is key to obtain relevant information. The work is being carried out in close cooperation with the other WPs, especially using the tools described in WP2 and networking activities under WP1. Among other expected results, WP3 will impact on the creation of a sustainable network of specialised Digital Innovation Hubs, where public investments are serving several regions of Europe.

Task 3.2 has been implemented in close connection with all the activities and tasks under **WP3- Upgrade of the Catalogue of DIHs**, and especially the assessment of the DIHs part of the Catalogue and the **Working Groups** launched with the aim to create a dynamic means of supporting and reinforcing collaboration among DIHs, so that a good input for the creation of a sustainable network of specialised DIHs.

This Deliverable is also in close connection to other Deliverables already submitted such as:

- D 1.1. Action Plan for the Working Groups, part of WP1, submitted by TECNALIA in M6.
- D2.1 Launch of the collaboration platform for DIHs, part of WP2, submitted by FundingBox in M4
- D 2.3: Maturity Assessment tool, part of WP2, submitted by TECNALIA in M6.
- D 3.1: Guidelines to update and upgrade the Catalogue, part of WP3 submitted by TECNALIA in M6.
- D 3.3: Common Approach for Maturity Assessment, part of WP3, submitted by TECNALIA in M8.

The following chart shows how this deliverable is framed within the DIHNET.EU project:

1.3 Objectives of Deliverable 3.2

Main aim of **Deliverable 3.2** is to suggest the **DIH vision and mission for the Community of DIHNET.EU**; taking as a basis the JRC Catalogue and the DIH assessment performed. The DIH Community is growing with new DIHs and networks of DIHs, most of them part of the Catalogue. Nowadays the Community is populated by 347 members and 3 networks of DIHs have also joined; we are in close contacts with several other networks of DIHs that are willing to join. Through the Community, we try to better understand the DIH needs to keep and active and connective Community where DIHs can interact, match-make and grow; we also plan mechanisms to keep this Community active, aligned and coherent with relevant policies, all this to reach the vision and mission. For this purpose, the following activities are being implemented:

- **Assessment of DIHs from the JRC Catalogue** as a main input for the other activities.
- **Identification of the DIH Community:** we have identified and continue to identify who is part of this Community (competence centres, incubators, research organisations, investors, SMEs,

large companies, industry associations, incubators, governments, H2020 projects- CSAs, IAs, networks of DIHs, other related projects and programmes, DIHs, etc.). A classification of the Community Groups is provided; working groups have been created and activated with relevant participants. New DIHs are always invited to participate resulting from our dissemination activities as well as our participation in relevant events; networks of DIHs are also included.

- **Community needs:** in close cooperation with WP1 (Task 1.2), the Community needs and demands (user groups, providers of funding, etc.) are asked with the final aim to better match interests, providing direct and indirect information, as well as distribution channels. A form/questionnaire has been defined and published in the Community to better understand the needs and demands, what works better, and which aspects will need to be improved in order to have an active and dynamic DIH Community (for details see section 3.4 below). We will encourage DIHs to answer these questions, as we plan to leave it open in continuation to obtain as many responses possible. The results will be checked and analysed when a relevant number of answers would be available. Working Groups are also a key tool to understand DIHs needs on specific topics.
- **Community planning and alignment:** several community actions are planned and aligned to increase linkages and expectative permitting to establish a vision and a mission with a common focus. The Working Groups established are a strategic tool to reach this scope.
- **Coherence with regional, national and EU policies:** policy alignment of the Community of DIHs and networks will be ensured taking into consideration main regional related strategies (e.g. Smart Specialisation, Digitisation, Industry 4.0, Smart Industry, etc.). This will be an important input to feed policy making in connection also to WP4, devoted to reinforce specialisation.

More in detail, the following KPI will measure performance.

Table 1: KPIs for measuring performance of the community

KPI nº	KPI name	KPI target	Success
KPI 2.1.	# of on-line platforms ready for supporting collaboration	1 platform	Reached in M4,
KPI 2.2.	# of thematic communities that are active and on-going by the end of the project	At least 8	4 reached in M6, as for Working Groups 3 specific targeted networks in M12
KPI 2.3.	# of connections among community members suggested through the matchmaking tool.	At least 80% of community members with a completed profile will receive a suggestion	347, Community members M12 Many stakeholders are part of the community, they are participating in WG (based on pre-selection criteria) where they can connect.

KPI 3.3.	# of forms to better understand the demand and offer hosted at the platform and filled in by DIHs	1 form filled in by 50% of the DIHs from the Catalogue	1 Form online to understand demands/interests from DIHs about the Community published at M10, we expect that at least 50% of the DIHs participating at the Community express their interests by means of the questionnaire. Questionnaire provided on the needs and preferences by DIHs, part of WP5, which can be seen as a demand assessment tool too. D 5.1: Segmentation of DIHs services and business models per thematic/ topic/ activities (M9)
-----------------	---	--	--

Associated Milestones: launch of the on-line platform (M4); Guidelines to update and upgrade the Catalogue (M6); Establishment of the Working Groups (M22).

2 DIH Community, vision and mission for the DIHNET Community

The **DIHNET.EU Community** is the **complementary tool to the JRC DIH catalogue** that allows DIHs to meet, exchange, discuss and identify which of their missing expertise can be found in other DIHs across the EU.

Yet, the DIHNET community and the JRC DIH catalogue are different tools under separate governance (DIHNET Community is led by the consortium while the Catalogue is maintained by the JRC). For example, DIHs that are not yet part of the JRC catalogue are still welcomed to become part of the DIHNET Community. This ensures that any DIH could benefit from the webinars, articles and news presented at the DIHNET community platform. Lessons learned from the DIHNET Community will be used to suggest recommendations for the JRC Catalogue. Next to this, the DIHNET Community provides guidance on how DIHs can also present a good candidature at the JRC Catalogue.

The Community also offers DIHs strategic information and permits them to interact, give opinions, learn from others, get trained and be informed on first hand of relevant information, etc.

The Community has now 347 members (30th October 2019) and four key initiatives supporting DIHs: SmartAgrihubs, AIOTI DIH Network, DIH2, I4MS have agreed to become part of the DIHNET Community, they are showcased under the following link: <https://fundingbox.com/c/dihnet-community-1/collections/showcase>. Similar initiatives have also been contacted and are in the process of becoming part of the DIHNET.EU Community.

The community will also host subcommunities, we currently have one created, called “Spanish Network of Digital Innovation Hubs”, led by planetec.es.

The Community is a key central information point for DIHs, some of the activities of DIHNET.EU Community are shown in the slide:

The Community aims to be the central information and discussion point of DIHs and networks of DIHs; as well as the place where interested stakeholders visit to get information, share their opinion and learn from others. The DIHNET.EU community includes communication and services to foster working in common, facilitate collaboration and find relevant information in order to support the creation of a sustainable pan-European network of networks, with a focus on regional DIHs.

DIHNET.EU **Community has the following mission and vision.** Both the mission and vision are connected to the essence of the DIHNET project. Project mission articulates the project’s aims and unifies the project team to reach that mission. It gathers and represents what the project does and how we do it. The vision sets the DIHNET project goals specially focusing the future.

DIHNET.EU Community Mission

- The **mission** of the Community is to **remain the largest interactive and dynamic community of DIHs** and a central information, connection and discussion point for DIHs.

DIHNET.EU Community Vision

- The **vision** of the Community is to **set the means and tools to keep DIHs connected**, permitting them to meet, exchange, discuss and identify which of their missing expertise can be found in other DIHs across the EU. **To support the creation of a sustainable European network of DIHs**, enhancing the collaboration, aligning and synchronizing of DIHs activities.

3 Activities supporting to reach the DIHNET Community mission and vision

The following activities support reaching the planned vision and mission. All these activities are in place at the moment, and thus at the time of reporting this Deliverable.

3.1. The DIHs assessment under the JRC platform

The Catalogue is hosted by the JRC platform. The Catalogue provides a comprehensive overview of DIHs in the EU across varying competences, structures and service offerings. It needs to be an alive and updated instrument that offers the information needed for DIHs as well as for the potential users (EU, regional and national governments, DIHs, SMES, mid-caps, entrepreneurs, etc.) to improve collaboration and ensure the networking among them. The consortium supports the JRC and DG Connect in the assessment process of individual DIHs, against the following four conditions shown in the following slide:

Every DIHs that presents its candidature under the JRC portal is carefully checked and assessed; in most of the cases recommendations for improvement of their profiles are sent to meet the 4 conditions. Once all conditions are met, the DIH profiles are published either as In Preparation (IP) or as Fully Operational (FO) ones; this this is the case when all conditions are fully met.

This assessment process is demanding many efforts and time, as most of the profiles do not meet the conditions for publishing at the first time, so several contacts and checks are needed before it could be published on the Catalogue and visualised on the Map.

The process in nowadays performed under the new JRC platform, that includes several changes from previous one. So far **more than 200 DIH applications have been assessed, out of which more than 40% of the DIH candidatures assessed published at the Catalogue** and visualised in the Map.

The Community also offers support and Guidance to DIHs on how to fill in the candidatures before presenting them to the Catalogue.

This assessment process allows us to identify DIHs that potentially can be part of the Community, as our Community also supports them to solve some of the challenges and doubts, they might have, so

both the Catalogue and the Community are feeding each other. There is also a learning resulting from this assessment to understand what works well and what does not together with challenges to meet that permits us to suggest improvements to the upgrade and update of the Catalogue, as well as having an overview of the European DIH landscape that can be fed into the further collaboration activities.

The Community is a platform for DIHs to network and cooperate, acceding competencies and facilities that might not be available at regional level; to transfer knowledge and the basis for economies of scale and investments in the DIH. In practical terms, the Catalogue provides a “**yellow page** of DIHs”; **Fact-sheets** with profile, contact data, service examples for regional, national, and EU-supported DIHs and a **Map-based search tool** by technical competences, market sector, services.

3.2. Identification and Classification of the Community Groups

The DIH Community is populated already by 347 members, including (competence centres, incubators, research organisations, investors, SMEs, large companies, industry associations, incubators, governments, H2020 projects- CSAs, IAs, networks of DIHs, other related projects and programmes, DIHs, etc.). We estimate that out of these members 73% are DIHs and the rest other organisations. On top of this, we also have four projects that already joined the Community (SmartAgrihubs, AIOTI DIH Network, DIH2, I4MS) and additional ones that are ready to join please see the following link for updated information (<https://fundingbox.com/c/dihnet-community-1/collections/showcase>). These four projects are already coordinating a network of DIHs, so DIHNET tries to ensure better coordination among them with the main aim of creating an active, dynamic and coordinated network of specialised DIHs, where the DIHs and related stakeholders create strong links for interacting. The four Working Groups in place are also grouping DIHs around specific thematic.

Among others the following target audiences and services were already identified under Deliverable 2.1 to be part of the Community:

- **Sectoral and technology oriented DIHs that aim at providing services to SMEs:**
 - Reinforcement of **services deployment**: Aims at providing them with information on how to improve their services about a systematic addressing the needs of their customers through the organisation of learning between the DIHs;
 - To facilitate **pan-European connections** between individual DIHs with a platform, both to create learning mechanisms as well as initiate collaboration.

- **Regional DIH initiatives, including regional DIH networks as well as regional initiatives like Vanguard:**
 - To reinforce **alignment and synchronisation** of the deployment of services and increase the impact of regional and national expenditures on digitization, developing a smart specialisation strategy on DIH.
 - Facilitate **access to pan-European capacities** (infrastructure and expertise) by offering tools to find these capacities they can easily implement at regional level.

- **EU DIH networks** (H2020 Innovation actions and CSAs, EC Preparatory Actions, Interreg projects), as well as **EU supported digital transformation initiatives**: EFFRA, IAs and CSAs in I4MS, SAE, photonics, robotics, HPC CPS/IoT. Projects like Smart Factories and Connected Factories also are included:
 - **Aligning the activities** of the different initiatives and creating a coordinated communication approach to the EU DIH community (improving impact);
 - Creating a **learning mechanism** between the initiatives to enhance efficiency and increase impact;
 - Create **common resources** to be used, like general communication materials, lists of contacts;
 - Organise a **common approach to the DIH Catalogue**, so information can be shared between the initiatives. The objective is also to create a governance structure.

- **European Commission services in charge of DIHs development and policy**:
 - **Aligning the activities** and policies devoted to support DIHs and Regions;
 - Obtain **direct feedback from the policy target** (DIHs, EU initiatives part of the pan-European network, DIHs networks).
 - **Bring the ecosystem directly involved in the implementation of the Digital Europe Programme together**, being able to select best practices, offer inspirational practical cases to lagging behind regions.

3.3. DIHNET.EU Working groups as facilitators

As already indicated, DIHNET.EU aims at fostering continuous sharing and networking amongst DIHs. Working Groups aim to get DIHs together around specific topics and make them cooperate and collaborate with a unique focus, approach and common understanding. The rationale behind is that they manage to get together to better understand and solve main concerns, exchanging experiences and good practices among themselves resulting in a depth learning exercise as well as in specific outcomes that will help DIHs to develop and grow.

Working Groups, as already explained under **Deliverable 1.1. Action Plan for the Working Groups** are a key tool to enhance collaboration and support the creation of a dynamic European DIH Community, as it is expected that out from their work, we can get very relevant and strategic information to:

- **Upgrade the Catalogue**, which is the main objective of WP3. These Working Groups will create enough information to have an indication of the European DIH landscape and concerns, that could also latter fed into further collaboration activities.
- Make the **EU DIH Community active**. Creating a place for DIHs to meet, learn, connect, exchange, discuss and to identify which of the missing expertise can be found in other DIHs across the EU.
- Contribute to the project in general and to the Catalogue and Community in particular, **with very relevant information**, making the Catalogue “**an alive instrument**” that offers the information needed for DIHs as well as for the potential users (EU, regional and national governments, DIHs, SMES, mid-caps, entrepreneurs, etc.) to improve collaboration and ensure the networking among them.

- Contribute to the creation of an **extended network** resulting from these interactions as well as to **concrete collaboration opportunities**.
- **Supporting regional, national and European policy**, stimulating the DIHs to create a vibrant European collaborative DIH Network that enables using the benefits from existing European capacities and expertise to enhance the European industry and innovation system at large.
- Combining **pan-EU complementary expertise** in developing innovative solutions.
- Better **identify and coordinate the DIH Community** with the main aim of creating an active, dynamic and coordinated network of specialised DIHs, where the DIHs and related stakeholders create strong links for interacting.
- Reinforce **alignment and synchronisation** of the deployment of services and increase the impact of regional and national expenditures on digitisation, developing a smart specialisation strategy on DIH.
- Etc.

The following Working Groups are operating in our DIHNET.EU Community:

1. **Finance and funding opportunities** (coordinated by FundingBox)
2. **Collaboration activities and mechanisms** (coordinated by euRobotics)
3. **Connection with regional and national policies and strategies** (coordinated by TECNALIA)
4. **Business Models and Sustainability** (coordinated by BLUMORPHO)

At a glance, each Working Group:

- Is participated by more than 25 DIHs (each DIH represented by 1-2 members).
- Is coordinated by one Project partner supported by a DIH.
- Meet at the Community and physically in average twice and in coincidence with strategic Workshops or events related to DIHs.
- Work on activating the group; on setting the purpose and outcomes; developing the strategy and policy implications.
- Communication and dissemination of the activities of these Working Groups are essential for the success of the work. A factsheet has been provided including the overall approach, purpose and progress. These Factsheets are disseminated and presented in different events.

A KOM was organised last 19th June for each of the WG; physical meeting was also organised in Brussels on 1st July during the 7th DIH Working Group meeting and we plan to meet at the Stakeholder Forum in Madrid next 13-15th November 2019. The rest of the work is on the Community.

3.4. Understanding the Community needs and demands

A **questionnaire has been published online** to understand the DIHNET Community member's needs. The objective will be to matchmake the interest of the community, providing direct and indirect information, as well as distribution channels. Promotion on social networks on this questionnaire will be also enhanced and supported.

It is a very simple questionnaire where we try to find out main interests, as well as what works well and what needs to be improved in the Community. As already indicated, the plan is to leave it open to have as much ideas possible for the DIH's interests. The questionnaire will be also distributed within the Working Groups.

The following questionnaire has been published under the following link: <https://fundingbox.com/spaces/dihnet-eu-community-dihnet-eu-news-events>,

It has the following structure and questions:

Dear participants of our DIHNET Community, as you know our Community is planned to support you and connect you with other DIHs, towards the creation of a sustainable network of DIHs this is why it will be very useful for us to understand which your specific needs are to match your interests as much as we can. We will very much appreciate if you can support us to improve the services provided by answering this brief questionnaire:

1. *Do you think the DIHNET. EU Community is useful for your DIH?*
 - *Yes; Please explain why*
 - *No; please explain why*
2. *What do you miss?*
 - a. *More webinars/trainings*
 - b. *More interactions between members*
 - c. *More exchange of experiences, tips from "mature" DIHs*
 - d. *Other:*
3. *What do you think has improved in the community since its launch?*
4. *Do you feel that the Community is supporting your DIH to improve collaboration with other DIHs?*
5. *In your opinion, how can we enhance the work inside the Working Groups to create valuable results for DIHs?*
6. *Do you have any further comments or suggestions about the DIHNET community?*

The Working Groups are also a very useful instrument to understand DIHs needs, challenges and demands. Several questions are launched to the group members and discussions around them are generated.

3.5. Community Planning and alignment

The Community structure was already presented under Deliverable 2.1 in Month 4. It is about a:

- Central Information Point
- Spaces
- Forms Gallery and Open Calls Management System
- Tool for Setting Up Local Communities
- Matchmaking Tool

The use of **Ambassadors**/experts is suggested to contribute to the community offering content in form of articles, webinars or other might be also considered as part of the strategy in order to offer a variety of information and contributions, and to attract new audiences and facilitate organic growth.

Impact Analytics reports for decision making at project and EC levels are planned where analytics will be reviewed at the Platform since the beginning of the Project, but first version, when relevant results are expected to be achieved.

The work at the Community is very dynamic, planning and alignment is continuously in place to increase the linkages, align expectative and to establish and reach a vision and mission with a common focus. The Working Groups are also a good input for this, as they have been organised under specific groups of interests around a thematic.

3.6. Coherence with regional, national and EU policies

Policy alignment of the Community of DIHs and networks is ensured taking into consideration main regional related Strategies (e.g. Smart Specialisation, Digitisation, Industry 4.0, Smart Industry, etc.). On top of this every DIH that is assessed and published under the Catalogue needs to fulfil this criterion and show alignment with policies such as Smart Specialisation, Digitalisation, etc. at EU, national and regional level.

A specific **Working Group** is in place to deal with the DIH connections to policies. This Working Group will focus on exploring the challenges and actions needed to ensure alignment and coherence of DIHs to the regional, national and EU policies and strategies to digitalise industry, especially to Smart Specialisation.

Among the challenges of this Working Group the followings have been stressed:

- Identify strategies at regional, national and EU level that support DIH collaboration.
- Identify mechanisms put in place to support cross-border/interregional/ national cooperation and technology transfer.
- Outline the contribution of DIHs to shape regional/national/EU digital transformation strategies.
- Determine the involvement of DIHs in the implementation of these strategies.
- Identification of Best Practices.
- Ensure DIH connection and alignment to the strategies

The following key questions were already under debate with DIHs:

- Are national, regional or EU strategies supporting DIH collaboration?
- Which are the mechanisms and strategies in place to support cross-border/interregional/national cooperation and technology transfer among DIHs?
- Are DIHs contributing to shape digital transformation strategies (regional/national/EU)? How are DIHs contributing to the implementation of these strategies?

The project team is also participating in several events where dissemination is targeting regions and members states such as the European Week of Regions and Cities last 7-10 October 2019 in Brussels with more than 9000 attendees.

4 Conclusions

The Community it is expected to provide high-quality and relevant data, evidence and insights that will be translated in specific suggestions for improvement of the Catalogue as well as for policy makers. The Catalogue needs to be a tool for Member States, regional governments and policy makers for understanding the state of the play of the nation/regional EU DIHs, and this is not yet the case. The Community and the Catalogue need to keep connected.

DIHNET aims to be the largest online community of DIHs and Networks of DIHs in Europe with the aim of allowing the DIHs stakeholders to share the information provided and to facilitate interaction and connection among the members to make it possible the creation of sustainable European network of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs). This is part of its vision and mission.

Yet, it needs to be recognised that there are many activities, initiatives and projects which simultaneously run community platforms which is not an easy task, as it might create complexity to the stakeholders who find it difficult to follow discussions and be active at many different platforms. DIHNET project is very aware of it, therefore special effort is devoted through the Community to keep DIHs informed and connected. The Working Groups have been very successful in engaging participants and very interesting questions have emerged. Additionally, DIHNET has presented the community and how it is built in meetings with other projects. This, as well as the other projects advertised on the DIHNET community show the impact of such broad DIH community platform.

All the activities described under this Deliverable are in place, to feed and populate the Community.